

AURES II Financial Research Template

Member State:

Author:

Date:

Interview recorded:

Please provide some information about your background (interview partner)

1. What are your contact details?

First Name	<hr/> <u>Please enter text here</u>
Last Name	<hr/> <u>Please enter text here</u>
Organisation name	<hr/> <u>Please enter text here</u>
Where is your organisation located?	<hr/> <u>Please enter text here</u>

2. What is your background in renewable energy investment?

- Project developer
- Utility/energy company
- Investment fund
- Private equity fund
- Commercial bank
- Multilateral development bank
- Insurance company
- Pension fund
- Energy cooperative
- Other (RES Financing expert)

3. What are your experiences in RES?

How many RES projects have you worked on (overall)?	<hr/> <u>Please enter text here</u>
Which countries did you invest in in the last 5 years?	<hr/> <u>Please enter text here</u>
How many employees work in your company (approximately)?	<hr/> <u>Please enter text here</u>
What kind of financing do you typically use for your projects?	<input type="checkbox"/> project based <input type="checkbox"/> balance sheet <input type="checkbox"/> both

Quantitative part

DIA Core and Re-frame: Cost of capital & WACC indicators

In a first step, please fill in the table below with the financial parameters for your Member State that were researched during the Dia Core. You can retrieve the data from the DIA Core website:

http://diacore.eu/?option=com_content&view=article&id=11.

Financial parameter	WACC	Debt/Equity ratio	Cost of debt	Cost of equity
Wind Onshore 2014				

Regarding the financial indicators for onshore wind and PV in 2016, please fill in the table below with the financial parameters for your Member State that have been researched during 2016 for the Re-frame project (see in the attached PPT document).

Financial parameter	WACC	Debt/Equity ratio	Cost of debt	Cost of equity
Wind Onshore 2016				
PV 2016				

Questions for focus countries:

Interview partner 1	Project 1	Project 2	Project 3	Project 4	Project 5	Project 6	Project 7	Project 8	Project 9	Project 10
Wind Onshore / Offshore investments 2018- 2019										
Country where the project is located										
WACC										
Debt/Equity ratio										
Cost of equity										
Cost of debt										
DSCR										
Loan Tenor										
Technology (please indicate in this field if the project is wind onshore or offshore)										
Size of project (or at least size categories)										
Time (year/date when it was the financial close or for what auction round did it bid)										

Type of financing (project finance, balance sheet)										
Type of investor (national, international, institutional inv., private inv. ...)										
Project phase (i.e. planning, construction, operating)										
Did you get additional support, e.g. financing from EIB, EBRD										
Financial closure,										
Completed construction										
PV 2018- 2019										
Country										
WACC										
Debt/Equity ratio										
Cost of equity										
Cost of debt										
DSCR										
Loan Tenor										

Size of project (or at least categories)										
Type of financing (project, balance sheet)										
Type of investor (national, international, institutional inv., private inv. ...)										
Project phase (planning, construction, O&M)										
Additional support, e.g. from EIB, EBRD										
Date of bid/auction										
Financial closure,										
Completed construction										

Qualitative part for all countries with auctions

A) Did the financial indicators, indicated below, change after the introduction of auctions in your country? If yes, please indicate how strongly the indicator has changed.

[indicate +- 10%-100% or more]

(assuming a p90 production scenario)	Before introduction of auctions	After introduction of auctions
Cost of debt (%)		
Cost of equity (%)		
DSCR (1.2, 1.5 etc.)		
Loan tenor (years)		
D/E ratio (80/20, 70/30 etc.)		

B) Why have these changes occurred? Please list the top 3 reasons of the changes above (reasons can be risks related to the project development – side of equity provider – or risks on a project financing perspective – side of banks). Please also rank the reason(s) according to their importance between 0 to 4. [0 means not important at all (i.e. not applicable), 1 slightly important, 2 important, 3 fairly important and 4 very important.]

C) Do the auction design elements mentioned in graph below affect your cost of capital / financing conditions)? Please evaluate each of these design elements according to their impact in the countries you have experience in.

Please introduce the name of design elements of the graph above in the fields of the table below.

Country 1

Ranking	Cost of debt	Cost of equity	D/E ratio	DSCR	Loan tenor
Very large effect					
Fairly large					
Important					
Slightly important					
Not important					

Country 2

Ranking	Cost of debt	Cost of equity	D/E ratio	DSCR	Loan tenor
Very large effect					
Fairly large					
Important					
Slightly important					
Not important					

Country 3

Ranking	Cost of debt	Cost of equity	D/E ratio	DSCR	Loan tenor
Very large effect					
Fairly large					
Important					
Slightly important					
Not important					